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The rules for memorizing English words

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Abstract: It is no exaggeration to say that English is one of the most developed languages in the world today. Learning it is also at a high rate among people. Of course, you cannot learn any foreign language without memorizing new words. This article also includes the rules and methods of memorizing vocabulary quickly and easily.

Key words: English, memorization, methods, new words, vocabulary, phrases, associative network, story method, pictorial method, matching method.

Memorizing new vocabulary is the main task in learning English. The article analyzes the methods that a teacher can apply to effectively memorize new words, and also discusses the techniques and methods for learning new material, taking into account the types of perception of information by students. The paper describes in detail the methods of visual and auditory perception, as well as various variants of mnemonics. In the study of foreign languages, students face various problems, including the effective memorization of words. The relevance of this issue lies in the fact that vocabulary replenishment is considered one of the main conditions for the successful learning of a foreign language. In this regard, students need to know what effective methods exist for this and how to use the techniques of memorizing English words for successful mastery of a foreign language. This article will consider the methods that researchers offer in modern

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scientific papers.

Before considering the ways of memorizing words, it is necessary to define such a term as memory. This is a property of the human brain that allows you to record, store and, if necessary, reproduce information. Memory can be divided into 3 main types: sensory memory, short-term memory and long-term memory.

Creating associative networks

Our brain takes what we read and turns it into images, ideas, and feelings, and then makes connections between the new information and what we already know. This is how memorization happens - the new merges with the old. Imagine a tree. Isn't it easier to see a sprawling tree with many branches and leaves than a small tree with a few branches? The same goes for the brain. When you associate a new word or concept with something you already know, it's easier for your brain to find and remember it at the right time.

Memorizing phrases

Remembering the word is important, but English, like any other language, is not just a collection of concepts, it is a tool that people use to communicate and express themselves. Find examples of how a particular word is used in the text. Write not only the word itself, but also its neighbors.

Use pictures

Draw small pictures to remember the meaning of the word. Don't get a drawing? Don't worry, it's better than that. Our brain receives such monotonous information that a strange picture has its own surprise, and we always remember unexpected events. Our brains are better at reading visual information. Draw a funny picture that shows the meaning of the word and you will remember it faster. English

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learners often complain that there are too many new words and it is difficult to remember them.

Make up stories

There is one trick you can use to learn words quickly. Make up any story, even a funny one, in which all English words are involved. Imagine this in detail. The method of adaptation to the Uzbek language

A student memorizing words in English may face another interesting situation. It is also the fact that some English words are not only in tune with Uzbek words, but also have the same meaning. Of course, there are few words like this, but through effort and research, you can find many such words and increase your vocabulary even more.

Below are examples of such words:

To chop – chopmoq

Daddy – dada

The wall – devor

A voice – ovoz

Asphalt –asfalt

Learning new words in context. This technique is effective in memorizing polysemantic words or set expressions. As an example, the author considers the word fair: "If, for example, the word "fair" is encountered, and it means "fair", but this does not fit the context, then I give the phrases a fair mark - a fair assessment, a fair price - a fair price, a fair weather - favorable weather, a fair boy - a blond boy".

In addition, the author of the article gives some tips for more productive work

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in English classes. For example, from a synonymous series of words, one should learn those words that correspond to the level of the student: “In grades 5-6, it is enough to know the meaning of the word noisy - noisy: a noisy boy, a noisy town. And in the 8th phrase, the noise and bustle of the city are expressed by the words hustle and bustle”. In addition, the unit of stored information should be as long as possible. In other words, it should not be one word, but a block of words or a phrase. Students also need to understand the difference between the words used and distinguish them in context. And finally, remembering words should not be the goal. It should be only an action leading to the achievement of some goal.

In conclusion, we can say that the use of a memory card, singing, storytelling, as well as various mnemonic methods greatly facilitates the process of learning a language, allows you to immerse yourself in the language environment, provides long-term memorization and develops speaking skills and understanding of English speech.

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